

Tutorial on mining of biomedical literature with the help of R Package

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Abstract

This paper provides step by step process involved in mining of biomedical literature using R-Statistical Package. Abstract from PubMed database on a given topic are retrieved, stored, pre-processed using R programming codes. The resultant term document matrix is used to find association between terms and frequency of the terms in each document. Finally the clouds of words and clustering of documents are created using the R software to discover the association between the documents. The results from the process provided a step by step understanding of the retrieval of abstracts, pre-processing of abstracts and clustering of abstracts using the user based query term

Keywords: Biomedical, Clustering, Classification, R Software, Text mining

Full Paper

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